

Downscaling magnetic field gradients for structured copper magnetoelectrodeposition on the micrometer scale

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ABSTRACT

Electrochemical deposition in magnetic field gradients is a promising method to synthesize structured deposits by exploiting the magnetic field gradient force. Typically, magnetic field gradient templates with dimensions in the millimeter range are used, but a downscaling is desirable from fundamental and application points of view. In the present study, pulse reverse plating of copper is performed in combination with four successively downscaled magnetic field gradient templates, which consist of three iron wires with diameters of 1 mm, 500 μm , 250 μm , and 125 μm . Structuring is demonstrated for all four templates, upon downscaling the Fe diameter within the templates. The deposited copper structures closely resemble the calculated profile of the magnetic field gradient term $B \nabla B$. The application of more negative deposition potentials leads to improved structuring. Based on the analysis of the current transients, this effect is explained by the action of the curl of the magnetic field gradient force, which profits from the faster development of a steep Cu^{2+} concentration gradient due to the earlier transfer from a charge-transfer-controlled to a diffusion-limited deposition mode. Significant differences in morphology, ranging from needle-like growth to smooth deposits, are obtained, which vary with the magnetic field gradient profile and the deposition voltage. The results demonstrate that the combination of tailored magnetic field gradient templates and optimized electrochemical parameters offers an advanced route to control the shape and morphology of structured Cu deposits at the micrometer scale, with potential applications in microelectronics and catalysis.

1. Introduction

Magnetoelectrochemistry comprises the analysis and technological exploitation of the effects of magnetic fields and their gradients on electrochemical reactions. The complexity of the considered processes, involving aspects of electrochemistry, magnetism, magnetic materials, and fluid dynamics is challenging for fundamental research [1]. Nonetheless, this field is rapidly growing towards envisioned applications, e. g. in electrodeposition [2–6], electrolyzers [7–10], corrosion control [11,12], or chemical machining [13]. The application of magnetic fields during electrodeposition promises an increase in efficiency due to enhanced deposition rates [4,14], and when using inhomogeneous magnetic fields, the perspective of a cost-efficient mask-less deposition

of structured deposits [2].

In this work, we focus on Cu electrodeposition, which is a relatively simple yet industry relevant model system that has also been studied before [15–18]. Copper layers have broad applications mainly due to their high thermal and electrical conductivity, especially in the electronics industry [19,20]. In early works, systematic investigations of Cu magnetoelectrodeposition were performed by exposing homogeneous magnetic fields with varying field strength to a working electrode in either parallel or perpendicular configuration [16,17,21]. In the perpendicular configuration, electrolyte convection is induced by the Lorentz force $\vec{F}_L = \vec{j} \times \vec{B}$, with \vec{j} being the current density vector and \vec{B} being the magnetic flux density vector. This induced convection leads to a decrease of the diffusion layer thickness and causes enhanced

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deposition rates when depositing in the diffusion-limited regime, compared to the case without magnetic field [1,16,18,22]. This effect is often referred to as the macroscale magnetohydrodynamic (MHD) effect [2,23].

In recent years, the research on electrochemical processes in heterogeneous magnetic fields providing local magnetic field gradients has been increasingly intensified. In this case, the magnetic field gradient force $\vec{F}_{\nabla B}$ becomes an important additional force that can affect electrodeposition. $\vec{F}_{\nabla B}$ is defined as [15,24–26]:

$$\vec{F}_{\nabla B} = \frac{\chi_{sol}}{\mu_0} (\vec{B} \cdot \vec{\nabla}) \vec{B} \quad (1)$$

with $\chi_{sol} = \sum_i \chi_{mol,i} C_i$

where χ_{sol} is the solution's magnetic susceptibility, given by the weighted sum of the molar magnetic susceptibility $\chi_{mol,i}$ multiplied by C_i , the concentration of all the species i in the electrochemical system. μ_0 is the free-space permeability, and $(\vec{B} \cdot \vec{\nabla}) \vec{B}$ is the magnetic field gradient term [2,27–30].

Specific experimental setups aiming at analyzing magnetic field gradient effects with minimal superposed MHD effects were developed to attain a fundamental and theory-based understanding. Such setups typically use magnetic templates with millimeter-sized magnet arrays that generate large and well-defined calculable magnetic field gradients in the vicinity of the electrode surface. *Structuring*, evidenced by lateral differences in thickness and morphology of the deposits [15], which are correlated to these magnetic field and magnetic field gradient patterns can be obtained here [29,30].

Tschulik et al. [2,15,25] first utilized an „Fe wire template“ consisting of an array of 21 pure Fe wires with a diameter of 1 mm. Surprisingly, the lateral differences in topography of Cu deposits increased when successively decreasing the Cu^{2+} concentration from 1 M to 0.1 M, even though the overall nature of the electrolyte solution changed from paramagnetic ($\chi_{sol} > 0$) to diamagnetic ($\chi_{sol} < 0$) in this concentration series. This observation cannot be explained by $\vec{F}_{\nabla B}$ in the general formulation (Eq. (1)). Considering fluid dynamics principles, it became clear that in closed electrochemical cuvettes, only the rotational part of the force can generate electrolyte convection [22]. Therefore, the curl of $\vec{F}_{\nabla B}$ plays a crucial role in inducing the local flow responsible for the structuring [15,29]. The curl of $\vec{F}_{\nabla B}$ can be formulated as:

$$\vec{\nabla} \times \vec{F}_{\nabla B} = \frac{1}{2\mu_0} \left(\sum_i \chi_{mol,i} \vec{\nabla} C_i \right) \times (\vec{\nabla} B^2) \quad (2)$$

and is thus determined by the gradient of the squared magnetic flux density ($\vec{\nabla} B^2$), the molar magnetic susceptibility $\chi_{mol,i}$ of all species i in the electrochemical system, and the concentration gradient $\vec{\nabla} C_i$ of these species. Eq. (2) shows that in order to drive electrolyte convection, a concentration gradient must exist for a non-vanishing curl of the magnetic field gradient force. During Cu deposition, a concentration gradient builds up for the electroactive Cu^{2+} ions, consumed at the WE. Because molar magnetic susceptibility of the paramagnetic Cu^{2+} ions ($\chi_m(\text{Cu}^{2+}) = 1.57 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ m}^3/\text{mol}$) [28] is largest among all species in solution, only the Cu^{2+} gradient is relevant for the structuring [29,30]. The improved structuring at lower Cu^{2+} concentration can then be explained by considering the time evolution of the Cu^{2+} diffusion layer in front of the WE surface: at lower Cu^{2+} concentration, metal ions are depleted in a short time, and thus the deposition quickly becomes diffusion-controlled [15].

Experiments of Dunne et al. [30] confirmed the essential role of a Cu^{2+} concentration gradient to achieve structured Cu deposits in magnetic field gradients. Here, arrays of millimeter-sized cylindrical NdFeB magnets were used as magnetic field gradient templates. Structured

deposits that closely mirror the magnetic field pattern on the lateral millimeter-size scale were obtained. The best-developed patterns were found at intermediate deposition times. This finding was explained by the time-dependent evolution of the diffusion layer thickness and the associated $\vec{\nabla} C_{\text{Cu}^{2+}}$: initially, the diffusion layer needs some time to build up, and then it continuously grows into the electrolyte, which decreases the concentration gradient for long times.

Tschulik et al. [28] further showed that enhanced structuring is possible by pulse reverse plating (PRP) from a low-concentrated electrolyte solution (0.01 M CuSO_4) and using the 21 Fe wire template. This way, separated 3D Cu deposits with a diameter of ~ 2 mm were achieved.

The downscaling of magnetic field gradient effects and thereby a reduction of the lateral structure size of 3D deposits from the millimeter to the micrometer scale is exciting for both fundamental research and practical application. This would be important, e.g., for an envisioned application as a mask-less structuring method for Cu electrodeposition in view of further miniaturization of electronic devices.

So far, only few experiments targeted structured Cu electrodeposition in magnetic field gradients with lateral structure sizes below millimeters. Dunne et al. [31] used small rectangular magnets arrays with magnet widths down to 500 μm and achieved Cu deposits with thickness and texture variation approximately replicating the magnet arrangement and dimension. In a first provisional approach, Tschulik et al. [28] transferred the PRP experiment to a template with vertically embedded Fe foils with a width of 50 μm and achieved separated, Cu-enriched line patterns with a lateral width of about 200 μm . Recently, the PRP experiment was further developed by Huang et al. [32] by using a template composed of three Fe wires with a diameter of 500 μm . After 30 PRP cycles, a Cu deposit with a lateral width of about 1 mm and a height of about 2 μm was obtained above each Fe wire.

Decreasing the size of the magnets in the magnetic field gradient template seems to be an obvious route to downscale the size of the structured Cu deposits. When the characteristic length scale of the magnetic field gradient decreases [29], the relative importance of the local Lorentz force versus the magnetic field gradient force also decreases, which should be beneficial for downscaling in general. Large magnetic field gradients are still desirable for good structuring at smaller scales, as this facilitates the electrodeposition of structured Cu deposits [33]. Sufficiently large magnetic field gradients ($|(\vec{B} \cdot \vec{\nabla}) \vec{B}|$ of $> 10^6 \text{ T}^2/\text{m}$) could in principle be attained at micrometer-sized lateral dimensions, e.g., when using thin films with artificially patterned magnetic domains [34]. However, to date, there is no systematic experimental study assessing the downscaling of structured Cu deposits obtained by magnetic field gradient templates, and several obstacles are expected. One envisioned problem is the growing importance of viscous forces when flow effects induced by magnetic field gradients become restricted to regions very close to the WE surface. Furthermore, in addition to the dimensionality of the magnetic field gradients, the dimensionality of the concentration gradient is also decisive for the action of the magnetic gradient force. According to Eq. (2), a significant effect of the magnetic field gradient force can be expected only in regions where both the magnetic field gradient and the concentration gradient are large and orthogonal to each other [29,31]. In this respect, the control of the extension of the diffusion layer seems equally important as the magnetic field gradient scale. So far, the Cu^{2+} concentration and the deposition time have been identified as important parameters to control the evolution of the diffusion layer and thereby also the structuring [15,30]. However, the impact of the deposition potential has not been addressed yet.

The present work presents a systematic study of how the structuring during Cu electrodeposition changes when a tailored magnetic field gradient template is successively downscaled while using optimized cell design and electrochemical conditions. In continuation of the latest PRP experiment [34], a magnetic template design of three Fe wires was

selected. The diameters of these three Fe wires were progressively reduced from 1 mm to 500 μm , 250 μm , and 125 μm . Magnetostatic simulations were performed for all cases to calculate the local $|\vec{B} \cdot \vec{\nabla} \vec{B}|$ distributions at the working electrode surface. The topography and morphology of the deposits were analyzed by profilometry and scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Particular emphasis was placed on analyzing and understanding the effects of reduced magnetic field gradients at smaller scales and varying deposition potentials on the structuring.

2. Experimental

2.1. Electrochemical cell design and magnetic Fe wire templates

All electrochemical measurements were performed at room temperature in an open three-electrode cell within a cylindrical container made of Teflon (Fig. 1). The working electrode (WE) was a commercial glass plate, from Angstrom Engineering, with a diameter of 15 mm, a thickness of 150 μm , and covered with 50 nm of sputtered gold. For the surface of the gold layer, atomic force microscopy (AFM) revealed a root mean square roughness of 1.5 nm and a ratio of 1.023 between the true surface area and the geometric surface area (Supplementary Material, Figure S1). The WE was positioned at a circular opening at the bottom of the electrochemical cell, facing upwards. The opening was sealed with an O-ring. The geometric area of the gold surface exposed to the electrolyte is defined by the area of the opening, which is 78.5 mm^2 . From the AFM study, assuming a homogeneous surface, a true surface area of 80.5 mm^2 is estimated. This value is used to calculate the current density. The volume of the electrolytic solution was 20 mL. A platinum sheet counter electrode (CE) was placed at the top of the cell. The reference electrode (RE) was a Mercury Sulfate Electrode (MSE, $E_{\text{MSE}} = -0.65$ V versus Standard Hydrogen Electrode). The three electrodes of the electrochemical cell were connected to a Bio-Logic SAS VSP potentiostat.

Preceding tests based on the potentiostatic electrodeposition method described by Tschulik et al. [15] were performed with a 21 Fe wire template and different concentrations of CuSO_4 ranging from 0.001 M to 0.1 M in an aqueous solution of pH 3 (not shown). In agreement with the work of Tschulik et al. [15], good structuring was obtained for the low Cu^{2+} concentrations, while a well-defined structuring effect was not observed for 0.1 M CuSO_4 . However, the deposition rate was very low for the 0.001 M CuSO_4 solution. In order to achieve structured Cu deposits in a reasonable time, we therefore selected an aqueous solution of 0.01 M CuSO_4 with pH 3, adjusted by adding sulfuric acid, as electrolyte.

Four magnetic templates were prepared by inserting three pure Fe wires of different diameters d_{Fe} of 1 mm, 500 μm , 250 μm (from Goodfellow, 99.95 % pure), and 125 μm (from Mateck, 99.50 % pure) in

upright orientation into the three pre-drilled holes in a PVC template. The Fe wires have a length of 5 mm and a center-to-center distance of 2 mm. The wires were secured with epoxy resin and left to harden for 24 h. Top view optical images of the four templates are shown in Fig. 2. The magnetic templates were placed behind the WE, and the Fe wires were fully magnetized with two stacked NdFeB magnets (each with a height of 10 mm and a diameter of 20 mm) placed behind the Fe wire template.

The absolute value of the magnetic field gradient term $|\vec{B} \cdot \vec{\nabla} \vec{B}|$ at a distance of 150 μm above the upper wire surfaces, corresponding to the Au/electrolyte interface of the WE, was calculated for all four template configurations with COMSOL Multiphysics 5.6. To that aim, the NdFeB magnet was modeled as sintered NdFeB (N35) from the COMSOL AC/DC materials library and the Fe wires were implemented as soft magnetic iron through their non-linear B-H curve as a magnetization model, again provided by the COMSOL materials library. The mesh was discretized with free tetrahedral elements. The field provided by the NdFeB magnet ranges from $\mu_0 H_z = 0.60$ T at the very magnet surface (lower wire end) to $\mu_0 H_z = 0.28$ T at a distance of 5 mm (upper wire end). This results in a flux density of $B_z > 2.2$ T throughout the Fe wires.

2.2. Electrochemical methods

Initially, the open circuit potential was recorded for one hour to allow the electrochemical system to attain equilibrium. Cyclic

	Magnetic template	$ \vec{B} \cdot \vec{\nabla} \vec{B} / \text{T}^2 \text{m}^{-1}$
$d_{\text{Fe}} = 1 \text{ mm}$		
$d_{\text{Fe}} = 500 \mu\text{m}$		
$d_{\text{Fe}} = 250 \mu\text{m}$		
$d_{\text{Fe}} = 125 \mu\text{m}$		

Fig. 2. Optical images (left column) and calculated $|\vec{B} \cdot \vec{\nabla} \vec{B}|$ at a distance of 150 μm above the wire surfaces (right column) for all four Fe wire templates. The optical images for $d_{\text{Fe}} = 250 \mu\text{m}$ and $d_{\text{Fe}} = 125 \mu\text{m}$ appear similar with regard to the diameter due to the insertion of Fe wires into three pre-drilled holes with the same diameter of $\sim 350 \mu\text{m}$ in the PVC template.

Fig. 1. Sketch of the three-electrode electrochemical cell with the magnetic template.

potentiodynamic polarization (Cyclic voltammetry, CV) studies were conducted to identify suitable reduction potentials for copper deposition and to analyze the anodic dissolution regime. The potential was scanned at a scan rate of 5 mV/s from the open circuit potential ($E_{\text{OCP}} \approx -0.20$ V vs. MSE) to -1.50 V vs. MSE, then reversed to $+1.00$ V vs. MSE. Finally, it was scanned back to the E_{OCP} .

The electrodeposition of copper was performed using pulse-reverse plating (PRP). This method consists of cycles of deposition and dissolution steps; the underlying concept of PRP is described in detail in Ref. [28]. During the deposition step, constant deposition potentials (E_D) of -0.90 V, -1.10 V, or -1.30 V vs. MSE were applied for a deposition time t of 60 s. The deposition time was previously optimized for the electrochemical cell configuration with an iron wire template with $d_{\text{Fe}} = 1$ mm. After the deposition step, partial dissolution of the deposited copper was accomplished by linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) from -0.35 V to -0.20 V vs. MSE with a scan rate of 5 mV/s. The deposition step and dissolution scan were repeated 10 times. Preliminary studies with varying cycle numbers showed that 10 cycles yield a satisfactory structuring on a 1 mm diameter Fe wire template, while fewer cycles result in a less pronounced effect. All the measurements were performed without and with different magnetic templates placed behind the WE.

2.3. Characterization of the electrodeposits

Overview images of the copper deposits from PRP experiments were obtained from optical microscopy (KEYENCE, VHX 7000). Contact profilometry (Bruker, DektakXT) was performed to measure the height profiles of the deposits and to assess changes in surface roughness across different magnetic field gradient regions. After the removal from the electrochemical cell, the working electrode exhibits a curved surface, likely resulting from the pressure of the O-ring in the electrochemical cell during the electrodeposition process. To ensure accurate profilometric data, a baseline was established by selecting reference points between the copper structures deposited in the high $|\vec{B} \cdot \vec{\nabla}| \vec{B}$ areas. The homogeneous copper thickness was then subtracted as background. This procedure corresponds to the one used in Ref. [32]. The positions in-between the wires, where no magnetic field gradient is present, then provide a reference point with the height value z set to zero. Figure S2 in the Supplementary Material shows exemplary results of a profilometric analysis in the as-measured and corrected stages.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM, Zeiss Leo Gemini 1530) was employed to analyze the deposit morphology. Besides the top view analysis of as prepared samples, images with the sample tilted at 50° were taken. The lateral size of the surface protrusions was measured using the software ImageJ by drawing a single line within a top-view SEM image, and measuring the lateral size of all the protrusions on this line. An example of the measurement is shown in Figure S3 in the Supplementary Material. The data was further analyzed using the Origin software. Based on the Gaussian distribution of the measured values, an average size was obtained and used for plotting the graphs. To obtain the maximum height of the protrusions, the five highest protrusions were measured on the SEM images with the sample tilted at 50° . Selected Cu deposits were cut with a Helios 5 CX Focused Ion Beam (FIB) device to observe the cross-section in the SEM.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Calculations of magnetic field gradient product profiles upon downscaling the Fe wire template

Fig. 2 displays optical images and the calculated magnetic field gradient product of the four Fe wire templates (the detailed profiles are shown later in Fig. 4). The right column displays the magnitude of $(\vec{B} \cdot \vec{\nabla}) \vec{B}$, which is crucial for determining the curl of the magnetic field

gradient force ($\vec{\nabla} \times \vec{F}_{\Delta B}$) and characterizes the local forces acting towards the WE. The full mathematical formulation of $|\vec{B} \cdot \vec{\nabla}| \vec{B}$ and the comparison of its x -, y -, and z -components are given in Section S4 in the Supplementary Material. In Figure S4 it becomes obvious that the profile and magnitude of $|\vec{B} \cdot \vec{\nabla}| \vec{B}$ is dominated by $[(\vec{B} \cdot \vec{\nabla}) \vec{B}]_z$, which is much stronger than the x - and y - components. Fig. 2 shows that for the Fe wires with $d_{\text{Fe}} = 1$ mm, the maximum of $|\vec{B} \cdot \vec{\nabla}| \vec{B}$ occurs at the rim of the wires, in agreement with previous works [15,25,28]. However, for $d_{\text{Fe}} < 500$ μm , the profile of $|\vec{B} \cdot \vec{\nabla}| \vec{B}$ changes, with the largest values exactly above the center of the wires. Furthermore, the calculations indicate a significant decrease in $|\vec{B} \cdot \vec{\nabla}| \vec{B}$ as the diameter of the Fe wires decreases (note the change in the scale bar), from 1400 T^2/m for $d_{\text{Fe}} = 1$ mm to 250 T^2/m for $d_{\text{Fe}} = 125$ μm . This is mainly caused by the reduced magnitudes of \vec{B} generated near smaller Fe wires.

The calculated decrease in $|\vec{B} \cdot \vec{\nabla}| \vec{B}$ with decreasing diameter of the Fe wires is easiest understood by considering its largest contribution $B_z(\partial B_z / \partial z)$ (see S4 in the Supplementary Material) and the known decay of the magnetic flux density as a function of the extent of the field source [35]. For a saturated wire, at the very surface, the B_z is identical to $0.5 \mu_0 \cdot M_s$ (M_s is the saturation magnetization of the material) [35], irrespective of the wire diameter, but B_z decays faster with distance to the surface for small diameters.

At a distance of $z = 150$ μm , the Fe wire with the largest diameter ($d_{\text{Fe}} = 1$ mm) creates a maximum B_z of 0.4 T, while for the smallest Fe wire diameter ($d_{\text{Fe}} = 125$ μm), the maximum B_z reduces to 0.05 T. The gradient contribution $\partial B_z / \partial z$ is rather independent on the Fe wire size concerning absolute values, but is responsible for the shape of the $|\vec{B} \cdot \vec{\nabla}| \vec{B}$ profile. The gradient $\partial B_z / \partial z$ is largest at the wire rim, where the magnetization abruptly reduces to zero. For the largest Fe wire diameter, and thus small relative distances to the surface (150 $\mu\text{m}/1$ mm = 0.15), this leads to the enhanced magnetic field gradient product at the wire rim. For the smallest Fe wire diameter with a larger relative distance (150 $\mu\text{m}/125$ μm = 0.83) to the field source, the spreading of field lines with distance smears out the profile and results in a maximum magnetic field gradient product on top of the wire center.

3.2. Impact of deposition potential and magnetic template scales on the current density

To achieve an overview of the electrochemical processes and to select suitable potentials for the PRP experiments, cyclic voltammetry with and without employing the magnetic field templates was performed (Fig. 3).

In the absence of a magnetic field applied to the electrochemical cell (black curve in Fig. 3), the initiation of Cu deposition is noted at $E = -0.33$ V vs. MSE, and the reduction peak of $\text{Cu}^{2+} + 2e^- \rightarrow \text{Cu}^0$ is observed at $E = -0.79$ V vs. MSE. At more negative potentials, Cu deposition becomes diffusion-controlled, resulting in an approximately constant current density. At potentials lower than about -1.40 V vs. MSE, the further increase in cathodic j indicates the start of the hydrogen evolution side reaction. After the potential reversal, the dissolution of Cu is reflected in an anodic peak.

The CVs obtained with magnetic templates exhibit the same overall characteristics as those recorded without a magnetic field. However, when a magnetic template with $d_{\text{Fe}} = 1$ mm is applied (red line in Fig. 3), a higher cathodic current density is observed in the potential range from -0.79 to -1.50 V vs. MSE for diffusion-controlled deposition, compared to the case without a magnetic field. This indicates that the gradient of the magnetic field enhances the Cu deposition rate, consistent with previous findings [15]. This enhancement is also evident from the increased area of the subsequent Cu dissolution peak in the anodic scan.

Fig. 3. CVs for 0.01 M CuSO_4 (pH 3) without applying a magnetic field gradient and with a magnetic template with $d_{\text{Fe}} = 1$ mm. The inset shows a zoomed region of CVs when magnetic templates with different Fe wire diameters are applied, focusing on the potential range for deposition. The subsequently selected deposition potentials and dissolution range for PRP experiments are marked in the graph as red and green arrows, respectively.

The inset shows that the enhancement of the cathodic current density in the diffusion-controlled regime becomes less pronounced when smaller Fe wire diameters (250 μm and 125 μm) are used for the template, even though the analysis is hampered by current density fluctuations here. Such fluctuations of the cathodic current density in the diffusion-limited regime of Cu deposition have been previously observed in low magnetic field gradient setups and attributed to the effects of natural convection [33]. The area of the Cu dissolution peak is slightly larger for the case with a magnetic template (not shown for all Fe wire diameters), compared to the case without a magnetic template. This is another indication that a magnetic field gradient-induced enhancement of deposition is also achieved at smaller Fe wire diameters. Nevertheless, the changes in the CV induced by the magnetic field gradient templates in the present case are much weaker than those observed by Tschulik et al. [15]. In that previous study [15], 0.1 M CuSO_4 solution (pH 3) and a 21 Fe wire template with $d_{\text{Fe}} = 1$ mm were used, while the area of the Au surface exposed to the electrolyte was the same as in our experiments. Therefore, in the present work, the reduced number of only three Fe wires in the magnetic template, with Fe wire diameters of ≤ 1 mm, and the lower Cu^{2+} concentration can explain the lower impact of the magnetic field templates on the overall current response in the CV.

For subsequent PRP experiments, three potentials of -0.90 V, -1.10 V, and -1.30 V vs. MSE were selected for the deposition step, as these are in the diffusion-limited regime for Cu deposition, yet prior to the potential for water reduction. The anodic potential range of the LSV used for the partial dissolution step in PRP was chosen to be a linear sweep from -0.35 V to -0.20 V vs. MSE, similar to the PRP experiment proposed by Tschulik et al. [28].

Multiple Cu deposit samples were then prepared by 10 PRP cycles, for the three different deposition potentials and for the four magnetic field gradient templates. For each case, exemplary current density transients and associated charges for each deposition and dissolution step are presented in Figure S5 in the Supplementary Material. We mainly focus on the first cycle for simplifying the discussion. Fig. 4(a) illustrates the first cycle (current density versus time) of the PRP experiments. All $j(t)$ transients of the deposition step possess the typical shape expected for Cu electrodeposition when a constant potential is

applied in the diffusion-limited regime [36,37]. At the very beginning of the experiments, the Cu ion concentration near the WE surface is similar to that of the bulk electrolyte solution and the reduction of the Cu ions is mainly charge-transfer controlled. The ongoing reduction reaction then causes the depletion of copper ions in front of the WE, establishing a concentration gradient (∇C) and a change to diffusion-controlled deposition. The initial increase of the cathodic current density up to the maximum value j_{max} in the first cycle is related to the nucleation and diffusion-limited growth of 3D clusters [36–38]. For all subsequent deposition steps, a higher j_{max} than in the first cycle is reached directly after switching to the reduction potential (see Figure S5 in the Supplementary Material). This difference can be explained by the absence of nucleation in subsequent cycles, as the nuclei formed in the first cycle continue to grow. For all cycles, the following decrease of the cathodic current density originates from the increase of the diffusion layer finally reaching a plateau when the steady-state diffusion-limited deposition rate is reached [33,37]. The transfer to the diffusion limited regime occurs faster in the second and all subsequent deposition steps, in comparison to the first step. This explains the slightly higher charge recorded for the first deposition steps in all cases (Figure S5 in the Supplementary Material). The steady state is characterized by the limiting cathodic current density j_{lim} , which we define as the cathodic current density at the end of the deposition step ($t = 60$ s) in the following. In the subsequent partial dissolution step, the anodic current density gradually increases over time due to the ramping of the potential in a positive direction. A similar charge is transferred for all dissolution steps (Figure S5 in the Supplementary Material).

Fig. 4(a) shows that the deposition potential has a strong influence on the maximum cathodic current density. In addition, an influence of the magnetic templates on $j(t)$ during the deposition step can clearly be observed. The behavior during the dissolution step is similar for all experiments. To analyze the impact of the deposition potential and the magnetic templates on $j(t)$ during the deposition step in more detail, we extracted j_{max} and j_{lim} from multiple measurements and plotted their mean value and standard deviation as a function of the Fe wire diameter for all three deposition potentials in Fig. 4(b) and (c), respectively.

Fig. 4(a) and (b) show a clear increase in j_{max} and a shift of the

Fig. 4. (a) Current density transients of the first cycle of the PRP experiments for Cu deposition from 0.01 M CuSO₄ (pH 3) at different potentials (vs. MSE) and with Fe wire templates of different d_{Fe} and without magnetic template (“No B”). (b) j_{max} and (c) j_{lim} extracted from (a) and multiple similar measurements versus the different Fe wire diameters of the magnetic templates and without the applied magnetic template (assigned as $d_{Fe} = 0$).

Fig. 5. Profilometry line scans of Cu deposits obtained after 10 cycles of PRP with different deposition potentials vs. MSE (three left columns) and calculations of $|(\vec{B} \cdot \vec{\nabla})\vec{B}|$ at the Au/electrolyte interface (right column) for the four templates with Fe wire diameters of (a) 1 mm, (b) 500 μm , (c) 250 μm , and (d) 125 μm . In all cases, the line profiles were collected above the centers of the three iron wires in the applied template. For the case of $E_D = -1.10$ V vs. MSE and a template with $d_{Fe} = 1$ mm, the optical image of the copper deposit is presented as an inset, showing the location of the scan line as a white line.

maxima towards shorter deposition times with increasingly negative deposition potential. Both trends are in line with previous works and can be explained by the faster deposition in the initial charge-transfer controlled regime and an increase of nucleation density with more negative potential [36–38]. The concentration gradient ($\vec{\nabla}C$) is higher at a more negative potential, which leads to a faster transfer of the deposition mode into the planar diffusion-controlled regime. Fig. 4(b) also shows that there is no obvious and systematic effect of the Fe wire diameter on j_{max} . This indicates that the magnetic field gradients do not influence the charge-transfer kinetics and the nucleation mechanisms at the beginning of the deposition.

In contrast to j_{max} , the limiting cathodic current density j_{lim} , shown in Fig. 4(c), systematically decreases with decreasing d_{Fe} for all three deposition potentials, approaching the value when no magnetic template is applied. Thus, as expected from previous works [33], the steady-state diffusion-controlled Cu deposition rate decreases with decreased magnetic field gradients. In this diffusion-controlled regime, the deposition potential has no obvious influence anymore, as expected.

3.3. Impact of deposition potential and magnetic template scales on the structuring

In order to assess the impact of the deposition potential and the downscaling of the magnetic field gradient templates on the structuring, profilometry was performed on the samples after 10 PRP cycles, in addition to optical microscopy (Figure S6 in the Supporting Information). Fig. 5 shows profilometer results when using the magnetic templates with the four different Fe wire diameters and the three different deposition potentials. The calculated gradient products for the different Fe wires are given in the right column of Fig. 5. In all cases, profilometry reveals that structuring of the deposits was achieved by the magnetic field gradient templates. The different shapes of the deposit's topography across the samples clearly mirrors the calculated gradient product at the WE surface, for all potentials applied. The left-right asymmetry, clearly visible in the outer Fe wires of the gradient product profile for Fe wire diameters of 1 mm and 500 μm , arises from the superposition of wire stray fields and is directly reflected in the corresponding topography profile. This outcome aligns with the findings described in [25,28,33], i.e. that the Cu deposit is thicker at the rim for Fe wires with a diameter of 1 mm. For smaller Fe wire diameters, the deposit structure develops a single maximum above the wire center, also in qualitative agreement with the calculated gradient product profile. The transferred charge and thus the amount of Cu deposited per PRP cycle decreases by some percent when templates with smaller Fe wire diameters are used (Figure S5 in the Supplementary Material). For comparison, we performed a control experiment for $E_D = -1.10$ V vs. MSE with 12 PRP cycles (instead of 10 PRP cycles) for the template with $d_{Fe} = 125$ μm , thereby reaching a similar total charge and thus amount of deposited Cu as with 10 PRP cycles for the template with $d_{Fe} = 1$ mm. Profilometry revealed that the shapes of the deposits obtained with 10 and 12 PRP cycles are similar (Figure S7 in the Supplementary Material), ruling out that the change in shape is only due to a smaller amount of Cu deposited. This result evidences that shape control of the deposit topography can be directly achieved by the design of the magnetic gradient template and the resulting magnetic field gradient product.

The magnetic field gradient-induced topography variations were confirmed for selected cases by SEM cross-sectional images. For the case of a template with an Fe wire diameter of 1 mm and a deposition potential of -1.30 V vs. MSE, characteristic cross-sectional SEM images of the resulting Cu deposit after 10 pulse-reverse cycles are depicted in Figure S8. The thickness values, derived from averaged measurements taken across various images, amount to ~ 200 nm in areas with vanishing gradient product (between the positions of the Fe wires), to ~ 380 nm in an area with low gradient product above the center of the central Fe wire (~ 200 T²/m), and ~ 500 nm in high gradient product regions

above the rim of the central Fe wire (~ 900 T²/m).

The structuring height, Δz , is defined as the difference of the heights of the deposit at positions above the wires and in between the wires. Fig. 5 clearly shows that the structuring height decreases when downscaling the Fe wire diameters in the magnetic field gradient templates, at constant deposition potential. This can be readily explained by the decreasing magnitude of gradient product and thus, decreasing the magnetic field gradient force ($\vec{F}_{\nabla B}$). In this case, the local flow induced by $\vec{F}_{\nabla B}$ and the associated local enhancement of deposition rate becomes less pronounced. This finding is also in agreement with the lower limiting current density observed with decreasing Fe wire diameters in Fig. 4(c).

Fig. 5 reveals that a significantly improved structuring is achieved when using a more negative deposition potential at a constant $|(\vec{B} \cdot \vec{\nabla}) \vec{B}|$. For the template with the smallest Fe wire diameter of 125 μm , the decrease of the deposition potential from -0.90 V to -1.10 V and -1.30 V vs. MSE seems to be necessary to achieve a clear structuring (Fig. 5(d)). The beneficial effect of a more negative potential on the structuring can be understood in view of the enhanced charge-transfer controlled reduction and nucleation rate at the beginning of the experiment (see Section 3.2 and Fig. 4(b)). The higher initial deposition rate results in a stronger concentration gradient ($\vec{\nabla}C$) and a faster depletion of metal ions near the electrode surface, thus an earlier change from the charge-transfer controlled to the diffusion-limited deposition. This directly impacts the curl of the magnetic field gradient force ($\vec{\nabla} \times \vec{F}_{\nabla B}$), which depends on the concentration gradient (see Eq. 2), and which is a prerequisite for the $\vec{F}_{\nabla B}$ -induced local flow. From a mechanistic point of view, the beneficial effect of a more negative deposition potential on structuring is analogous to that reported previously for a decreased bulk concentration of Cu²⁺ [15]: both enable the faster transition from the charge-transfer to the diffusion-limited deposition regime, where the reaction rate is more significantly affected by electrolyte convection.

3.4. Impact of deposition potential and magnetic template scales on deposit morphology

The profilometry results in Fig. 5 also indicate that the roughness of the deposits varies with the magnetic field gradient and the deposition potential. The roughness of the copper deposit seems to be increased at locations with higher magnetic field gradients and for more negative deposition potentials. In order to analyze the morphology variations in more detail, we performed SEM of the surface at different characteristic locations on the samples.

We first discuss the dependence of the deposit morphology on the magnetic field gradient profile when the template with the largest Fe wire diameter of 1 mm and $E_D = -1.30$ V vs. MSE were applied. For this case, Fig. 6 displays the topography profile, the gradient product ($|(\vec{B} \cdot \vec{\nabla}) \vec{B}|$) and selected SEM surface images for the Cu deposit in the region above the central Fe wire. The SEM images reveal a strong non-uniformity of the morphology. At the rim of the Fe wire, where the gradient product is large, the surface protrusions are clearly elongated in the z-direction, with some needle-like protrusions reaching several microns in height. In the region of reduced magnetic field gradient above the Fe wire center, the copper protrusions are smaller, although some still show elongation. In regions with vanishing gradient products, the protrusions are not elongated and the deposit is smoother. These morphology differences are also confirmed by cross-sectional SEM images (Figure S8 in the Supplementary Material). The observed trend in roughness agrees with previous works, where smooth deposits in regions of low magnetic field gradient products and very rough deposits in regions with high magnetic field gradient products were also observed [15,25].

Fig. 6. Profile of a PRP Cu deposit with $E_D = -1.30$ V vs. MSE above the central Fe wire with $d_{Fe} = 1$ mm (black line) and the corresponding calculated $|(\vec{B} \cdot \nabla) \vec{B}|$ (red line). At the bottom, SEM images of the Cu deposit with the sample tilted by 50° are shown for different spots: areas with negligible $|(\vec{B} \cdot \nabla) \vec{B}|$ (green frame) outside the location of the Fe wire, with low $|(\vec{B} \cdot \nabla) \vec{B}|$ above the wire's center (blue frame), and with high $|(\vec{B} \cdot \nabla) \vec{B}|$ above the rim of the Fe wire (red frame). The frames indicate the approximate measurement position for SEM.

However, the extremely elongated needle-like protrusions registered in areas with the highest magnetic field gradient forces have to the best of our knowledge not yet been reported before. SEM images in Figure S9, S10 and S11 in the Supplementary Material show that these needle-like protrusions only occur when a sufficiently negative deposition potential is applied during the deposition pulse. The occurrence of such dendritic growth is typical for electrodeposition at very negative potentials and low metal ion concentration, which can be explained by the growth mechanism under diffusion control [39,40]. A more negative deposition potential favors a high deposition rate at the beginning of the deposition

pulse (see Fig. 4(a)). Cu^{2+} ions at the working electrode surface are thus rapidly reduced, thereby creating a concentration gradient in front of the electrode. Under this condition, occasional taller protrusions benefit from the non-zero Cu^{2+} concentration at a short distance from the working electrode surface, allowing them to overgrow their neighbors [41]. Nishikawa et al. [42] previously advanced a similar hypothesis, investigating the morphological changes in electrodeposited copper resulting from various concentrations of $CuSO_4$ solutions (0.20 M, 0.10 M, 0.05 M, and 0.02 M) at elevated current densities by SEM imaging. They found that the initiation of dendritic growth in copper

Fig. 7. Profile of PRP Cu deposit obtained with $E_D = -1.30$ V vs. MSE above the central Fe wire with $d_{Fe} = 125$ μm (black line) and the corresponding calculated modulus $|(\vec{B} \cdot \nabla) \vec{B}|$ (red line). At the side, SEM images of the Cu deposit with the sample tilted at 50° collected at an area with vanishing $|(\vec{B} \cdot \nabla) \vec{B}|$ (depicted by the green square), and an area with high $|(\vec{B} \cdot \nabla) \vec{B}|$ above the center of the Fe wire (highlighted by the red square) are displayed. The frames indicate the approximate measurement position for SEM.

electrodeposition coincides with the depletion of Cu^{2+} ions at the WE surface.

When downscaling the magnetic field gradient templates, the inhomogeneity of the deposit morphology becomes less pronounced. This is exemplarily discussed in the following for a PRP Cu deposition of 10 cycles using the magnetic template with the smallest Fe wire diameter of $125\ \mu\text{m}$ and $E_D = -1.30\text{V}$ vs. MSE. Fig. 7 shows the associated topography profile, the calculated gradient product and surface SEM images of the deposit obtained in a region with maximum gradient product above the center of the Fe wire and in a region with vanishing gradient product. Only small differences in the morphology of the Cu deposit between those two regions are observed, with protrusions appearing to be a bit more extended above the center of the Fe wire, where $|(\vec{B} \cdot \vec{\nabla}) \vec{B}|$ is larger. Compared to the case of larger Fe wire (Fig. 6), the deposit is in general much smoother. This may be linked to a less advanced grain growth connected to the reduced deposition rate, which is evidenced by both the lower cathodic current density (compare Fig. 4(a), and (c)) and the smaller deposit thickness of $\sim 100\ \text{nm}$ (according to the cross-sectional SEM image in Figure S12 in the Supplementary Material).

To assess possible general trends in morphology with a downscaled magnetic field gradient and varied deposition potential, we carried out SEM of the surface of exemplary Cu deposits for all studied cases. Here, we focus on the deposit regions with the maximum magnetic field gradient. Figures S9-S11 in the Supplementary Material summarize top-view SEM images for all cases and SEM images with the sample tilted at 50° for selected cases. We estimated the average lateral size of the surface features from the top view SEM images and the maximum protrusion height of the Cu deposits from the SEM images with the sample tilted at 50° , with the results summarized in Fig. 8(a) and (b), respectively. The evaluated lateral protrusion size is not strictly equivalent to the lateral grain size, as columnar growth is not always present (see e.g. Figure S8), but it can still be used as an indication for the grain size evolution.

Fig. 8(a) indicates that in general smaller average lateral protrusion sizes are achieved at more negative deposition potentials. Although this is not fully systematic here for all magnetic templates, such a trend is in line with a higher nucleation density expected at more negative potentials and aligns with previous findings of smaller lateral grain size with more negative deposition potentials [36–38,42].

Fig. 8(b) shows that for deposition at $-1.30\ \text{V}$ vs. MSE, the maximum protrusion height continuously decreases with decreasing Fe wire diameters in the magnetic template. The SEM images in Figure S10 and

S11 in the Supplementary Material clearly evidence this trend. For the more positive potentials of $-1.10\ \text{V}$ the trend is similar but less pronounced (see also Figure S9). However, at $-0.90\ \text{V}$, this trend is absent, and needle-like growth does not even occur for the template with the largest Fe wire diameter (see also Figure S10). The transition from globular grains to a needle-like morphology with the application of more negative potentials is consistent with the literature [39].

Overall, Fig. 8(a) and (b) indicate that both the average lateral protrusion size and maximum protrusion height tend to decrease with decreasing Fe wire diameters. For more negative deposition potential, the lateral protrusion size also seems to decrease. This trend may be attributed to the reduced flow of Cu^{2+} ions enriched electrolyte toward the electrode when smaller Fe wire diameters exerting lower $|(\vec{B} \cdot \vec{\nabla}) \vec{B}|$ are used, resulting in thinner copper deposits for a given deposition time.

4. Summary and conclusions

The downscaling of structured electrodeposition by magnetic field gradients was systematically studied by performing pulse reverse plating of Cu with different deposition potentials on magnetic templates with decreasing Fe wire diameters of $1\ \text{mm}$, $500\ \mu\text{m}$, $250\ \mu\text{m}$, and $125\ \mu\text{m}$. In all cases, a structuring is achieved, with the profile of the obtained surface topography closely following the calculated magnetic field gradient product profile. As the shape of the $|(\vec{B} \cdot \vec{\nabla}) \vec{B}|$ profile changes with the size of the Fe wires in the template, different shapes of the structured surface topography of the Cu deposits are obtained accordingly. This finding underlines the potential of magnetic-field-induced electrodeposition for shape control of structured electrodeposits by designing specific magnetic templates. Next short-term studies could focus on changing the magnetic field gradient products by modifying the ratio between the length and the diameter of the Fe wires in micrometer-sized magnetic templates.

A noteworthy result of the study is that the application of a more negative deposition potential enhances the structuring. This becomes decisive in achieving good structuring, especially at small magnetic field gradients. Based on the analysis of the current density transients, the beneficial effect of a more negative deposition potential can be explained by the faster development of the diffusion-controlled deposition regime. The associated fast occurrence of a steep concentration gradient is expected to enhance the curl of the magnetic gradient force which is decisive for the local flow required for structuring [29,30]. This

Fig. 8. (a) Average lateral size of protrusions, and (b) maximum protrusions height and SEM images (only for cases $d_{\text{Fe}} = 1\ \text{mm}$ and $d_{\text{Fe}} = 125\ \mu\text{m}$) in high $|(\vec{B} \cdot \vec{\nabla}) \vec{B}|$ regions of Cu deposits obtained after 10 cycles of PRP. Values were obtained for various Fe wire diameters d_{Fe} at different deposition potentials (vs. MSE).

mechanism is analogous to the one previously reported for a lower bulk concentration of Cu^{2+} ions, which also leads to faster transfer from charge-controlled into the diffusion-controlled deposition regime [15]. Therefore, our study suggests that the deposition voltage can serve as an additional, so far overlooked control parameter to optimize magnetic field-induced structuring of electrodeposits, especially at small scales. As the diffusion layer thickness increases with time in the diffusion-controlled regime, leading to a gradual decrease of the concentration gradient, we expect that the optimization of the duration of the deposition pulse during PRP may offer further improvement of structuring in the future.

Further downscaling of magnetic-field gradient-induced structuring of electrodeposits thus seems likely in the future. An attractive vision could be the use of magnetic thin film templates, which avoid the cumbersome mechanical assembly of magnets and allow much smaller structure sizes. Innovative concepts for the design of ferromagnetic thin film systems have led to the creation of tailored magnetic domain patterns. Neu et al. [43] developed a technique for imprinting regularly arranged perpendicular domains of about 150 μm domain width and with tailored domain wall configurations into a Co/Pt multilayer sample using a so-called geometrical transformation. Alternatively, ion beam patterning of an exchange bias CoFe/IrMn layer system can create regular in-plane domain configuration with domain width down to 1 μm [44]. Ahrend et al. [45] already demonstrated the guided chemisorption of diamagnetic molecules in the stray field landscape of such thin film substrates. Stray field profiles measured across the domain boundaries [34] result in substantial magnetic field gradient products $|\left(\vec{B} \cdot \vec{\nabla}\right) \vec{B}|$ of $> 10^6 \text{ T}^2/\text{m}$, and suggest their use also for magnetoelectrodeposition. These field gradients, however, decay very fast (within tens of nanometers) with distance to the surface, and it is unknown so far, whether electrochemical processes can still be controlled at this size level and whether structuring still occur at these reduced dimensions. However, the electrochemical toolbox now available to enhance the structuring, with the Cu^{2+} ion concentration, the PRP routine, and the deposition voltage as possible control parameters, offers optimistic perspectives in this direction.

Our experiments reveal that the topography, thickness, as well as local morphology, and grain size of Cu deposits, can be adjusted in a wide range by combining magnetic field gradient templates and specific deposition potentials. Very rough deposits and needle-like growth related to diffusion-controlled deposition are found at high magnetic field gradient positions (at the rim of the Fe wires with $d_{\text{Fe}} = 1 \text{ mm}$) when the most negative potential ($E_{\text{D}} = -1.30 \text{ V vs. MSE}$) is applied. Therefore, on the one hand, less negative deposition potentials should be employed to avoid dendrite growth and obtain smooth structured deposits in high magnetic field gradients. On the other hand, dendritic growth is beneficial when high surface area structures are required, e.g. for catalysis and energy conversion devices. Nonetheless, the effect of the deposition potential on morphology was different at smaller magnetic field gradient scales ($d_{\text{Fe}} = 125 \mu\text{m}$), revealing smoother deposits also when the most negative potential was applied. In this context, electrodeposition is already a versatile synthesis method, with morphologies tunable by electrochemical conditions [40,46]. The present study shows that the combination of designed magnetic templates with laterally varying magnetic field gradients in combination with a sufficiently negative deposition potential can be an efficient route to lateral morphological patterning on the microscale. Smooth and dendritic patches are achieved within one sample at specific locations defined by the magnetic field gradient template. Such magnetic-gradient-induced morphological design may find applications in multi-fluidic devices and lab-on-a-chip devices in general, where so far morphological patterning is typically done by lithographic methods or surface scanning techniques [47].

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Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work, the authors used ChatGPT by OpenAI to improve the readability and language of the manuscript. The tool was employed solely for linguistic improvement and did not contribute to the conceptual, analytical, or substantive content of the paper. All intellectual and scholarly contributions are the sole work of the authors. After using this tool, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

F. Sgarbi Stabellini: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **A. Singh:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **I. Soldatov:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **R. Schäfer:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology. **M. Huang:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology. **G. Mutschke:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology. **V. Neu:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **A. Gebert:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **K. Leistner:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at [doi:10.1016/j.electacta.2025.145994](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.electacta.2025.145994).

Data availability

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in the Zenodo repository at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14959920>.

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